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Risk management in a complex multi risk unregulated environment

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Energy systems are one of the pillars of a civilization and their study for a better safer use is an absolute necessary activity. By Energy Systems we will understand complex systems including energy sources, transmission from one form to another, users, and their feedback to the system as a whole and the environment affected. Energy systems and the knowledge embedded in them were considered in such evaluation as being complex (CES) operating as cybernetic machines and supporting their own transformation from one state to another under clearly defined laws and rules [1]. A similar set of lessons resulted in the project phases with the conclusions from the existence and operation of natural energy system, as it was the case with the natural reactor Oklo [2].

As reported before in a research project on the risks in CES, started two decades ago in various environments and still ongoing [1-3;7-10] CES structure might be complex and diverse (with natural and artificial non intelligent and/or intelligent components). Modelling complex systems was performed as the existing approaches reflected in a large literature and the solutions proposed in [1-3] and were based on basic approaches from it [4-6].

The CES modelled have high uncertainties in their internal and external interactions and they need special approaches to risk definition and evaluation due also to their diverse structure, implying diverse type of challenges, which may induce diverse types of risks as in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Risk zones and types of risks in case of multi sources

Figure 2 illustrates sets of cases of single sources of risk (RS_i) and for multiple sources of risk (RM_k) which will require complex planning for emergency situations. Existing situation for CES demonstrated the need to move from considering static Emergency Planning (EP) by dynamic decision-making process to Dynamic EP both for single and multiple sources of risks.

Figure 2. Emergency planning development for single and multiple risks sources

A description of potential challenges and their impact to risk status for CES is in Table 1 for natural or man-made (normal and unforeseen cases) indicating the expected type of risk impact. Multiple challenges lead to high and even catastrophic risk situations, requiring complex dynamic planning for emergency situations. In the category of man-made a series of challenges due to diverse structures of CES (which may include artificial hardware, AI, biological ecological environments etc).

Table 1. Challenges to CES and their risk impact expert evaluation for one typical energy system [1]

Challenges L=low M=medium H= High H+ = increased high H++ = catastrophic	Expected singular type of risk impact			Expected multiple type of risk impact		
	SS_Design Basis	SS_Beyond Design Basis	SS_Catastrophic	MS_Design Basis	MS_Beyond Design Basis	MS_Catastrophic
Natural normal	L	M	H	L	M	H
Natural unforeseen	L	M	H	M	H	H+
Man made normal	L	M	H	L	M	H
Man made unforeseen	L	M	H	M	H	H++

For a CES the challenges lead to sets of expected singular/multiple type of risk. Their evaluation is considering their relevance from design point of view. The risks considered in sample calculated cases [9,10] were of the following types: SS / MS_Design Basis, Beyond Design Basis and Catastrophic Natural normal or unforeseen and Man made normal or unforeseen. The risk modelling in those cases uses innovative approaches with pragmatic solutions in high-risk unregulated environments [4,5]. CES in unregulated environments and with changing types of risk sources require description of multi risk types of emergency actions. Sample cases of such modelling from [7,8] were developed for multiple risk cases in [9,10].

In recent phases of the project to evaluate multiple risks for CES systems the goal was to identify specifics for situation when risks arise in CES operating in unregulated environments , as for instance in war type situation [9,10]. The description of the notion of risk for more advanced CES and how to manage it if the system has such a diverse structure and operates in unregulated environments is one of the challenges at the engineering phase of the future energy systems for our planetary and space developments. Risk management for CES of diverse types (man-made, environmental alive or not, including intelligent beings having AI incorporated), operating as carrying single type of risk (for instance nuclear) or multiple (nuclear, fire, population extinction etc) with the approach mentioned before [1,3,7,8] are already a top issue of real (unfortunately) life in many places and reflected in recent cases [9,10]. For the EP in CES in abnormal environments (unregulated with multiple risks) the Emergency Plans (EP) types are dynamic and create dynamic Emergency Categories (EC), as illustrated in Figure 3 may be defined in four quadrants depending on their relationship with type of risks (single vs multiple – S/M) and if foreseen or unforeseen (F/UF).

During an emergency, the EPs may change and the ECs also. ECs for instance in quadrants I, II, III, IV result for the situations of different EP types (“i” for EP and “j” for EC type (EC i EP j)).

Figure 3. EP and EC combinations for CES in multirisk situation

The risk evaluation generates states grouped in four categories (quadrants) in a plane defined by two axes: one of the types of risk sources (S/M) and the second of the type of challenge (F/UF). The results lead to combinations of ECs declared in a developed EPs. The combinations possible are as in Figure 3. The evaluation identified a dynamic change of EC to be declared depending on the variation of the conditions (from single to multiple sources and/or from foreseen to unforeseen challenges).

The results of the EP and EC evaluations, including the dynamic evolution of situation developed the basis for the decision-making process, which finally takes the mitigating actions for a complex, dynamic, and unregulated situation.

A supplementary uncertainty might be induced by the type of risk evaluation method used. For a regulated environment the basic assumption of the evaluations is that the criteria to judge applicability of a certain EP is based on a set of rules, i.e. CES operates in a regulated environment.

Table 3 includes the evaluation of the relevance performed using an approach of benchmarking different methods for risk evaluation, which were reported previously [8]. CES risks in emergency are evaluated for the Decision-Making Process (DMP) by using different methods like [8]:

- Precautionary principle
- Deliberative Principle
- Risk Informed Decision Making
- Aggregate method

The evaluation was performed for a real CES (nuclear power plant in war zone- complex system of diverse structure with single and multiple challenges and risk sources in an unregulated environment), for a series of possible states in which it may be before EP is declared [9,10]: EP in CES in unregulated environment with multiple risks. The cases considered in the evaluation areas in Table 2.

Table 2. Risk evaluation methods and their use for the decision-making process

Case	Description of case
A	Risk integration rules for single sources of risk $R^S I$ and static EP
B	Risk integration rules for multiple sources of risk $R^M K$ and static EP
C	Risk integration rules for single sources of risk $R^S I$ and dynamic EP
Envelope of ABC	Risk integration rules for multiple sources of risk $R^M K$ and dynamic EP

Another level of complexity of such tasks is generated by the a type of evolution not complying with any predictable rules (called jazz type) of the situation in general and in some particular case, i.e. a chaotic, in many cases unregulated development in consistent manner and set to operate in various security challenges environments. The capability to have strategies as the emergency plans proposed in [9,10] for those questions is a key feature of the stable development of protection reached by EP. The risk evaluations for cases in Table 2 were performed by using the methods from Table 3. The detailed description and results on the use of those methods are extensively presented in [8].

Table 3. Risk evaluation methods and their use for the decision-making process

Components of the Decision-Making Process and their impact on the final decision (N= No impact; H=High; M=medium; MH= Medium to High; L=Low; VL=Very Low) as resulted by using different risk evaluation methods	Risk evaluation methods [8]			
	Precautionary principle	Deliberative Principle	Risk Informed Decision Making	Aggregate conclusion
A,B,C = Categories as per	PREC	DELIB	RIDM	AGGREG
Communication	H	H	N	MH
Structure's interface	H	H	H	H
Monitoring	L	L	N	L
Monitoring Coordination	L	VL	N	L
Results	N	M	M	M
Analysis (independent) available	N	MH	MH	MH
Highest overall impact for various cases	A	B	C	ABC

The cases A,B, C, ABC are as per the definition in Table 2.

The results indicate that the decision-making process for CES of [9,10] type has the highest certainty if diverse combined risk evaluation methods are used for any case.

Based on the EP evaluations a set of detailed principles to be included for a particular situation of a CES in unregulated environment, subject to multiple risks are derived and are further detailed on going work [9,10]. The actions to be taken for dynamic ECs are defined and the EPs must consider the CES operation in an unregulated environment.

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List of abbreviations

CES	Complex Energy System
EP	Emergency Planning
EC	Emergency Category
SS_Design Basis	Single Source of Risk due to Design Basis events
SS_Beyond Design Basis	Single Source of Risk due to Beyond Design Basis events
SS_Catastrophic	Single Source of Risk due to Catastrophic events
MS_Design Basis	Multiple Source of Risk due to Design Basis events
MS_Beyond Design Basis	Multiple Source of Risk due to Beyond Design Basis events
MS_Catastrophic	Multiple Source of Risk due to Catastrophic events
EC _i ^{EPj}	“i” type of state evaluated for EP for a “j” type of EC
PREC	Precautionary principle
DELIB	Deliberative Principle
RIDM	Risk Informed Decision Making
AGGREG	Aggregate conclusion
DMP	Decision-Making Process
N	No impact on risk
H	High Risk
M	Medium Risk
MH	Medium to High Risk
L	Low Risk
VL	Very Low Risk
S/M	Single / multiple risk
F/UF	Foreseen or unforeseen risk
I,II,III,IV	Quadrants defining states of combinations for EP and EC combinations for CES in multi risk evaluations represented on the axes F/UF versus S/M